

>>Was Ayn Rand “correct”? And do we live in an “Idiocracy?”

In this letter:

- A short response to Ayn Rand’s “Atlas Shrugged” concept of the “moochers”
- The Divine Right to Rule as a MIMS [aka the “Philosopher Sage-king”]
- POS Theory
- Carl Sagan: the epitome of Orwellian government shill

MIMS 2.83 - P.O.S. Theory

The Truth No One Wants to Admit about the Reason Why We Are In a Pickle. How Carl Sagan Was a Manifested Symptom of the Real Problem with Our Society!

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Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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Best view at: <https://bit.ly/3L83RGv>

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Re: Why does our world go backwards even as our science and technology go forwards?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

Yes, you live in a *temporary* “Idiocracy.”¹ More people exist to whine, complain, ‘do-nothing’ or merely identify problems instead of solutions than ever before. The fact is that our Western society was built by better men², mostly white and Chinese, to escape the unliberal hellhole of feudalism. It was engineered to be free-thinking, and with a general slant towards egalitarianism that rapidly accelerated through to the 1960s and 1970s (in the United States, and Europe generally as colonialism ended) and then passed parity. Once parity was passed, useless philosophies which had invaded academia in the 1920s and 1930s, when it was acceptable and we had no real data on socialist, fascist (nationalist socialist) and communist genocide³, then came into their own growing prominence in the 1990s⁴. Since 1919, we now have data on failed Marxist nation-states⁵ and we have exposés about the cost of abortion eugenicide⁶, as well as the facts about the socialist origins of “critical theory”⁷ that leads us to [rightfully] suspect the academics’ [supposed] good intentions. Most of that has been discussed by the deposed (targeted for socialist enforcement) Ricardo Dufresne in “On the Uniqueness of Western Civilization.”

The fact is that the Enlightenment, while full of anglicists and Victorian racists⁸, is actually the fruit of a long bent of cultural development fueled by industrialization, colonization & exploration, gold and resources, etc. The entire world was and is racist. However, that does not make technological development⁹, mathematics¹⁰, rationalism¹¹, empiricism¹², dialectics¹³, and the rest¹⁴ of what underpins modern Western Civilization racist or worthless. What **is** worthless,

¹ And it was *designed* to be so. See: Agenda 2030 ^

² Smarter, stronger, healthier, healthier boundaries, and normal in socialization and not distracted by agendas; they also had much stronger testosterone.

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mass_killings_under_communist_regimes

⁴ The economic peak of the Federal Reserve System and United States’ dominance, culturally and geopolitically.

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_socialist_states

⁶ <https://openworks.wooster.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1012&context=blackandgold>

⁷ One should view the opening chapter of “On the Uniqueness of Western Civilization”
<https://www.amazon.com/Uniqueness-Western-Civilization-Critical-Sciences/dp/9004232761/>

⁸ Many of which practiced eudginics and fake sciences which begat the modern abortion and national security destroying abortion industry connected to bad science and evil. Be aware, though, that the entire world at that time was highly racist. In fact it still is, and only the modern liberalized society even tries not to be racist.

⁹ <https://www.cnn.com/2021/05/09/us/techno-racism-explainer-trnd/index.html>

¹⁰

<https://www.the74million.org/article/can-right-answers-be-wrong-latest-clash-over-white-supremacy-culture-unfolds-in-unlikely-arena-math-class/>

¹¹ <https://www.aei.org/op-eds/smithsonian-institution-explains-that-rationality-hard-work-are-racist/>

¹² <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27758933>

¹³ <https://aeon.co/essays/racism-is-baked-into-the-structure-of-dialectical-philosophy>

¹⁴ <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2343&context=dlr>

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is anything that violates the scientific method, empirical fact, and is mathematically unsound (like pseudotensors). What is worthless are **fake science 'studies.'**¹⁵ In a separate paper the author will tackle and destroy those lies and destructive movements, exposing them for what they are. But as for the present concern, we are interested in the kinds of people (mentally speaking) that destroy rather than build, hate rather than love, annihilate what was painstakingly put together because of the trials of difficult human existence from the neolithic and antiquity to feudalism, etc.. And for what, 'equity'? Equity is built, it isn't stolen, and it has a number to it on a Balance Sheet.

The simple fact is that Ayn Rand - the foremost female intellectual of the 20th Century, by far - correctly identified the problem long ago: the moochers and looters.

"Money is not the tool of the moochers, who claim your product by tears, or of the looters, who take it from you by force. Money is made possible only by the men who produce. Is this what you consider evil?"

So what is the tool of the moochers and looters? With her identified 'mystics' the answer is simple: keeping the people ignorant and superstitious (anti-empirical). But what do the moochers do?

→ They make the builders/producers/capitalists feel guilty about their intentions to **build for the sake of building**. This is personified in the story of Hank Rearden and his interactions with his family.

It would be difficult to pick a single chapter or scene from where Hank's family has abused him and his creativity to nearly criminal levels. But, in fact, there are many examples. The most heartbreaking, of course, is the two most central scenes to his life's sad spectacle are when he gives his wife a Rearden Steel bracelet¹⁶ and when she trades it with Dagny for common jewelry¹⁷. What is sad about that is firstly that the bracelet was made in a moment of triumph: of Hank over nature, and his creative will over the steel. Dagny, the last vestige of the men of old in her family of train tycoons, and unironically a tougher man than her brother¹⁸, trades Mrs. Rearden for the rarest piece of jewelry known to man: a one of a kind of a priceless material that has never existed. The reality, though, is that moochers only care about a plastic existence full of cheap consumerism, and meaningless platitudes. What happens from there is not the discussion of this paper, of course¹⁹.

But for the present what matters is that the elite powers of the world, fueled by money and money's power to extend power²⁰, influence, affluence, and access²¹, are setting up a neo-feudal society by taking advantage of pie-in-the-sky idealists²², be they socialist or otherwise. And the result of this is that they want to harness people's labor and skill, for next to

¹⁵ Literally of no value and discriminatory to boot. Notice all the last paragraph's references are just absolutely bonkers rubbish.

¹⁶ Chapter 2, "Atlas Shrugged"

¹⁷ Chapter 6

¹⁸ It isn't clear how Rand knew men would get physically weaker as the 20th century progressed.

¹⁹ The reader can enjoy the mimsical analysis in the new Aether Flow: Business Circuit Theory paper.

²⁰ "The Axioms of Power," Sf. R. Careaga

²¹ "The Axioms of Influence," Sf. R. Careaga

²² Optimists, Utopians, Pacifists, etc.

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nothing, for their own ends. Perhaps it will be SPACER ends, or perhaps the War Economy, but nevertheless, this is slavery. The robbery of property rights and freedoms of speech, of body-mind, and the sanctity of truth against the onslaught of digital propaganda and tyranny over privacy is tantamount to a reversal from liberalism into the age of the Divine Right to Rule. Pre-Magna Carta ideas, and the world of tribalism (via identity politics) are making a comeback, and it is mostly from the corners of the world and internet with low IQ and low TIQ²³. Why? Because people with low IQs cannot think of non-violent solutions. They are only able to come to one basic conclusion: "I can rob people and if it weren't against the law I'd get away with it."

But because it is against the law, and God's Law, they alter the words, change the history, falsify the data, and do whatever they can to hurt regular people and intimidate them. From porch-pirates to vulture capitalists there is only one common thread:

- ❖ They are all special, unique, sensitive, **pieces of shit** (P.O.S.) snowflakes²⁴.

The Allies of the P.O.S.; accomplices in crimes against Humanity

Since most people are either POS or work for them unwittingly, you cannot really throw a stone [in the proverbial glass house of the USA®] without hitting someone you know, or someone famous²⁵. Given that the last critical paper the author put out was about the Peer Review Cult²⁶, there is one P.O.S. which the author has in mind for exposing to the world, and pulling back more of that dyed-in-the-wool "stooge" from the eyes of John Q public.

There is one name which has been synonymous with adulation, undeserved if not for touching so many lives of young kids and scientists, and which is even more heaped up with the bullshit of the Cult than even Michael Shermer. That name, and that man, is Dr. Carl E. Sagan.

We shall briefly and with some depth, take a look at a government stooge that was not only part of coverups, but violated federal law by revealing his work on project A119, the "Nuke the Moon" project. But his worst crimes against humanity, by far, were his vicious and paid attacks upon Dr. Immanuel Velikovsky, a man who made enough predictions that if Sagan had done even one or two of these, would have earned him a Nobel Prize.

But before we break down the words and deeds of this P.O.S. and his ties to the Empire of Lies, let us first talk in general terms. How do the accomplices of the P.O.S. work? They work by:

1. Excusing the bad behaviors, unethical or immoral - even illegal - of the real P.O.S.
2. Aiding in or abetting the technocracy, and the lies of the elite knowledge/power brokers, especially the Fact-Checkers, mainstream media, journals, "chouralist" websites, and the entire filthy system of grants for federal cash.

²³ Technical Intelligence Quotient; literally the ability to use electronics and STEM, especially to solve daily problems.

²⁴ Aren't all 3rd and 4th wave feminists 'Stunning and Brave'? Nothing like claiming to want equality and what you really mean is supremacy, privilege, top-paying jobs with no responsibility for the fair share of danger and risk, and to top it all off, labeling easy jobs (like stay at home mother) as "the most difficult job in the world." (Oprah said this to resounding applause). What a load of rubbish.

²⁵ This must make Jon Stewart and Bill Maher's job really hard to do.

²⁶

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

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The system of non-builders, of takers, of welfare dependents and their pushers (addictors), government subsidies (which generate the fascist power the media substantiates with their lies and fake news), etc. is that which fuels the rape and unjustified destructions of:

- Families
- Religions
- Mom-and-pop businesses
- Communities
- The Middle Class
- The environment
- The Poor or Working Class
- Minorities (POC)
- Appalachians (especially white ones) or Scots-Irish, or Celtic-Welsh
- Free peoples (the indigenous)
 - And not in those particular orders

Why do they take from these people and objects? Because it is easy²⁷. Because there is money. Because parasitism is one of the earliest biological forms of existence now known²⁸. Because, and most importantly, “good men do nothing” and that includes good women, and religious leaders, etc. People who don’t do something when they can, or know they should.

The fact is that the P.O.S. and their accomplices are the same as the moochers of Rand’s story. They used to rely on the mystics for mind control, and now the mind-controllers have a unique reverse solution. Once children and people are controlled by the technocracy²⁹, the technocracy simply teaches people how to behave and think like the superstitious and mindless rabble of old³⁰. Pretty soon, at the rate we are going as a society with tearing down history³¹ and banning grades³², math³³, etc., the moochers won’t need even superstition or religion. They will simply say “do” and the chattel will do. In fact, historically the communists and fascists have hated and crushed religion³⁴. Instead, they will rely upon a new form of mysticism: Orwellianism.

²⁷ Weak protection and representation.

²⁸ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/6827186/>

²⁹ Mostly social media and algorithmic control.

³⁰ Within another generation it is possible that young people will use Harry Potter to explain how cellular smart phones work!

³¹

<https://www.nationalreview.com/2020/07/progressive-war-on-history-aims-to-erase-memory-founding-principles/>

³² <https://www.npr.org/local/309/2020/02/28/810325384/public-schools-try-ditching-a-to-f-letter-grades>

³³ www.theguardian.com/us-news/2015/oct/17/berkeley-math-professor-alexander-coward-campus-battle

³⁴ Nazi Germany and Mao’s China both had “cultural revolutions.” Both went hard on Judeo-Christians, Muslims, Buddhists, and energists (yoga, qigong, etc.).

The Most Orwellian Thing You Can Do...

Doublespeak, getting people to have double-think, or rewriting history, is not the most Orwellian thing one can do. The most Orwellian thing one can do is to convince people that they shouldn't trust their "lying eyes" when looking at obvious, indisputable results. When Dr. Velikovsky made several predictions which came true before the Space Era, the government was in the midst of a growing Military Industrial Complex, and had not one but **three** secret space programs³⁵. They were combined into one by President Kennedy (JFK): NASA. However, those programs were not the end of it - the secret space and electrical research - and just last year the US government, on directive of President Trump, combined all the Air Force's and CIA's space assets into the US Space Force in May of 2021.

But in the 1970s, fresh at their high power from arriving at the moon in 1969, and in conjunction with the corporate giants like Lockheed-Martin, the secret space program work was continuing unabated. Funding for NASA was at its peak, as compared to the US GDP. What they were into is covered (as mentioned in the other paper) in Greenwald's and Salla's books. What is relevant is that despite the previous history of eliminating "Worlds in Collision" and all of Dr. V's relevance from academia, that they went out of their way to challenge the old man, drag him from his retirement, and ruin him publicly. They [the MIC and Scientism establishment] couldn't have the public trusting a man who was right, not only despite the use of myth and religious history but **because of its accuracy**. The fact is that Dr. Velikovsky, and not Carl Sagan, made these following successful predictions:

1. Jupiter have a strong magnetosphere
2. Jupiter having radio waves
3. Venus to be hot, not cold
4. Venus to be rotating backwards
5. Venus to have a comet tail (not confirmed during his life)
6. Venus had a disturbed axial rotation³⁶
7. Venus in a continual stage of cooling (from the previous event)
8. Planetary and planetoid large electrical charge
9. Venus to have Carbon in its atmosphere

There are more, and all salient. Because the man was not illogical at all, but ignored nevertheless. Take a look at the Orwellian response of Sagan versus that of an intellectually challenged, but honest, man, Dr. Hess:

"We will also examine an occasional additional (1) "prediction" of Velikovsky – for example, that the Martian polar caps are carbon or carbohydrates. My conclusion will be that where Velikovsky is original (2) he is very likely wrong; and (3) that where he is right the idea has been pre-empted (sic) by earlier workers. There are also a large number of cases (see the epigraphs of this article) (4) where he is neither right nor original. ..."

³⁵ "Space Force: Our Star Trek Future," M. Salla 2021

<https://www.amazon.com/Space-Force-Future-Secret-Programs/dp/B097NKLFK2/>

³⁶ <https://videttearchive.ilstu.edu/?a=d&d=vid19671102-01.2.31&e=-----en-20--1--txt-txIN----->

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“To the best of my knowledge, (5) there is not a single astronomical prediction correctly made in Worlds in Collision with (6) sufficient precision for it to be more than a (7) vague lucky guess; and there are, as I have tried to point out, a host of claims made which are (8) demonstrably false. The existence of strong radio emission from Jupiter is sometimes pointed to as the most striking example of a correct prediction by Velikovsky; (9) but all objects give off radio waves if they are at temperatures above absolute zero. The essential character of the Jovian radio emission – that it is nonthermal, polarized, intermittent radiation, connected with the (10) vast belts of charged particles which surround Jupiter, trapped by its strong magnetic field – (11) are nowhere predicted by Velikovsky. Indeed, his “prediction” is (12) clearly not linked in its essentials to the fundamental Velikovskian theses.” ~Sagan, (13) “Scientists Confront Velikovsky” (1977)

(14) “We are philosophically miles apart because basically we do not accept each other’s form of reasoning — logic. (15) I am of course quite convinced of your sincerity and I also admire the (16) vast fund of information which you have painstakingly acquired over the years. (17) “I am not about to be converted to your form of reasoning though (18) it certainly has had successes. You have after all predicted that Jupiter would be a source of radio noise, that Venus would have a high surface temperature, that the sun and bodies of the solar system would have large electrical charges and (19) several other such predictions. (20) Some of these predictions were said to be impossible when you made them. (21) All of them were predicted long before proof that they were correct came to hand. Conversely (22) I do not know of any specific prediction you made that has since been proven to be false. (23) I suspect the merit lies in that you have a good basic background in the natural sciences and (24) you are quite uninhibited by the prejudices and probability taboos (25) which confine the thinking of most of us. (26) “Whether you are right or wrong I believe you deserve (27) a fair hearing.” ~Hess, chairman of the (28) Space Board of the National Academy of Science (1963)

* Numbers added are the author’s

We shall step through each of these points and really examine what is being said, and the workings of the Orwellian P.O.S. will be demonstrated, rote. In point of fact the condemnation (besides being stern) will become bolstered and strengthened by the inclusion of other words of the anti-prognosticator, and jealous loser (in historical terms), Dr. Carl E. Sagan. Whatever victory his momentary badgering of an old and retired professor might have been, the decades have not been scientifically kind to Dr. Sagan. Also his reasoning is beyond faulty. It is demonstrably pernicious, which is more of a scientific crime than anything except data manipulation (lying).

1. The pedantic, condescending use of quotations is the first positional move of an academic pandering to an already witting audience of haters of Dr. Velikovsky.
2. As it turns out, though, Dr. Velikovsky got more right as time has gone on, whereas Dr. Sagan, and his friends such as Dr. Hawking, got more wrong as time went on.³⁷
3. Once you see the second quote you can see that Sagan is being absolutely flippant and irresponsible in his assertions here. In point of fact he is reducing the uniqueness by claiming there is nothing here to see. Nothing unique or special. But in fact, both quotes

³⁷ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-myth-of-stephen-hawking/>

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are dripping with points which state the opposite. “Nothing to see here” is a problem, unless you fall for Orwellian re-writing of history³⁸.

4. So which is it? Is he right or not? He was clearly right, which makes Sagan **wrong**. As for the assertion Dr. Velikovsky is unoriginal, the fact is that all of the previous catastrophists didn't make as bold of claims or predictions/prognostications. More importantly they were *also* castigated by the Victorian era scientific establishment, particularly those tainted with Darwinesque Marxst-Atheist ideas, and a predilection to despising Jews and/or Easter Europeans (“Russians”)... we haven't come that far, it seems. The Herouni telescope issue proves that by itself³⁹.
5. “Worlds in Collision” is not a book about predictions. It is a book about the past, and it was actually part of a two part series, of which the original was “Mankind in Amnesia.”⁴⁰ All that happened in Worlds was that to describe the past one needed to understand the likely and potential mechanisms. There's nothing at all controversial about what Dr. Velikovsky asserted. He made no extraordinary claim, he only made a claim that was provable, and therefore scientific. More importantly, it was tested and proven in the course of scientific rigor, with empiricism, and not condescension. **It was not Dr. Velikovsky burning books, it was Harvard Astronomy!**⁴¹
6. Speaking of vague, where is the sufficient precision provided in describing what is “sufficient precision” for a historical comparative-mythology book? Dr. Velikovsky⁴² was not an astronomer publishing in astronomy journals. When he made his bones, Sagan was not even born, and when his book was born Sagan was merely 16 years old. Impudence!
7. Here we see the jealousy shining through.
8. At this point they are not demonstrably false, except those which are just normally wrong. However, the fact is that Dr. Velikovsky was right and deserved a Nobel Prize. Sagan is jealous of that fact.
9. This is literally a red herring. Dr. Velikovsky wasn't making flippant guesses based on Absolute Zero. The truth is that such statements by Sagan are just plain irresponsible and a bit cruel.
10. It is nice of Sagan to make the author's points about plasma-electromagnetism etc. However, how does this harm Velikovsky's assertions?
11. Again, his work is not about making scientific predictions, it is about discussing the psychological ramifications of true human history. The scientific predictions are the sequelae of the work. When you have ‘scientific bigotry’ this type of lying about the intentions of other scientists is common as a form of high-brow or elitist ad hominem. It is a disgusting tactic which is to be expected of the jack-boot thugs the government would hire. While there may not be direct proof Dr. Sagan was hired to be a hitman - yet - the reality is that he was in government programs and then he mysteriously was given money to help debate (and crush) Velikovsky. Is that a coincidence the reader is willing

³⁸ The irony of this is not to be missed. Chronus being Saturn and Chronology being the truth of history.

³⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/herouni>

⁴⁰ <https://www.amazon.com/Audible-Mankind-in-Amnesia/dp/B09PWJGG6W/>

⁴¹ <https://books.google.com/books?id=sVooDwAAQBAJ&pg=PT39&lpg=PT39>

⁴² <https://www.thecrimson.com/article/1950/11/24/velikovsky-replies-to-shapley-pt-the/>

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to accept, in the face of overwhelming conspiratorial factual history regarding the USA® and the military empire?

12. This is the most essentially honest thing he has said so far. Probably with a euphemistic smile.
13. The other most honest thing is the title, but what is dishonest is the fact that it makes it out like Velikovsky is the bully, and not the victim of a) book burnings and b) a lone man against an entrenched, even violent establishment which spent most of its invective not on his ideas, but upon his person. Note the year: 1977
14. This is a bit of a misleading sentence, albeit it is very honest. However there is only one form of reasoning which counts in empiricism: rational deduction.
15. It is convincing of Dr. Hess that he means well in making this and all following statements, because unlike Sagan he is not dehumanizing him, or turning him into an enemy of science. Just another scientist.
16. Technically it was decades of time Dr. V spent in acquiring the knowledge, and it is not knowledge which Hess was capable of replicating. So while he can talk about it circumspectly, and respectfully, he has not walked those philosophical miles he mentions. This is bad news for his own position, actually. But you can sense, unlike the predatory statements of Dr. Sagan, that these are the shaky statements of someone with a paradigm being challenged (and rightfully so).
17. He isn't specific about what form of reasoning he will accept? If mythic evidence is such a problem: why does it work?
18. That's all that really matters, and everything else is window dressing and gas-baggery.
19. More important than the predictions, let's focus on things no one wants to talk about. For example, how those woolly mammoths have food in their stomachs 1,000 miles from where they currently grow. Or how the calendars kept changing, and why Caesar would need a festival killing nine of ten bulls. Or how Saturn's rings ended up with those same isotopes as Earth's oceans. Etc.
20. Again, the proper response for these predictions is to award prizes. Instead, they awarded book burnings.
21. Note the date: Hess is mentioning this more than 10 years before Sagan, that all of Dr. Velikovsky's prognostications were in hand well before the space race. That is the open and shut case. Sagan is green with envy.
22. At that time this was true, but later some predictions that were made were not true, such as Venus atmosphere's carbon being hydrocarbons, whereas so far we are only sure of the carbon dioxide. However, the fact is if mana was hydrocarbons that rained down, a temperature as high as Venus' surface temps, and that much pressure (20x that of Earth) would lead to chemical organic compound changes. We might just not be seeing enough of the trace remaining amounts.
23. Hess' admission that Dr. Velikovsky had a good basic background in sciences is a gravel in the mouth statement, because in fact Dr. Velikovsky was brilliant in his logical attacks in "Cosmos Without Gravitation" for which he receives - to this day - little to no credit. Then again Nobel Laureate Dr. Hannes Alfvén had an amazing cosmological framework of stupendous quality and it is ignored, too.

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24. A strange way of admitting the scientific community is. I rest my case in that direction, having already dedicated a paper to proving the biases exist. Now a man in 1963 readily admits it.
25. The confinement is obvious in this very writing, for he refuses to accept logic that leads to the correct results. I must remind the audience that Sir Arthur Conan Doyle had Sherlock Holmes say a most true statement,
"Once you eliminate the impossible, whatever remains, no matter how improbable, must be the truth."
26. Well he was right, is my point. And honestly, the only point that is relevant, and the space scientific community should have capitulated in 1970. They did not. They let Sagan destroy the reputation of an old man already once castigated. To this day people like Graham Hancock refer to Mankind in Amnesia, but remain afraid to be "Velikovskied." In fact this is the only reason Graham is unwilling to review my work.⁴³ He

⁴³ Graham Hancock <gbhancock@gmail.com> Jul 10, 2021, 1:33 PM

Hi Ramon

Thanks. I've downloaded the two papers you linked to and will read over next few days,

Best wishes, Graham

Jul 12, 2021, 7:00 AM

Hi Ramon

The two papers you sent me links for both seem to assume a palaeo solar-system model in which Jupiter is extremely close to the earth -- and that at a time when humans were able to observe it.

Is that correct?

I don't have time to go fishing through your various papers (I note you reference an earlier paper or paper) to discover the logic behind this model. Send me a paper or a link to a paper you have written that makes that case.

Also to what extent, if any, are you basing yourself on Velikovsky?

Best wishes, Graham

The first paper is extremely straightforward. (Sorry for the length but this is an important conversation). Not only did they observe it but they had maths to engineer it and after the solar system rearranged they aligned the mounds up to help mark the solstices etc. These asymmetric octagons cannot fit any other model (though you are welcome to try). 3 different sites in Ohio. Though there were probably more. Moreover the Ramesses Stele has Jupiter and Saturn's diameter ratios to within 1% of satellite measurement. <http://bit.ly/2O7wCHS>

It also clearly references a solar orb with a ratio of 1.23

The worldwide cosmic egg also makes it clear we had a different star (Shamash or Ra). So do translations by Budge et al. about the star.

But when you look at Enclosure D of Gobekli Tepe the Vulture Stone which describes the orbit after breakdown is in the "hatching" portion of the stone. We see cross reference data at Maputo and Bakoni <https://bit.ly/3kfyJKV> (the spreadsheet of data is linked in there)

I actually don't have to rely on Velikovsky at all if I don't want to because the Chinese plasma glyphs and Native references including in Nahuatl are unambiguous.

The intro in my Megafuana Extinction has a number of important quotes.. *Some selected from your books...* And then Part 1 breaks a lot down. I most recommend you go through that as soon as you understand the rock hard mathematical implications of these 2 papers papers. (sic)

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is afraid to abandon an altstream position that becomes untenable and have his life's work be trashed. It need not be. It isn't trash. It just is like the rest of science: as of yet incomplete models. The Thunderbolts Project was closer to the truth because they unapologetically followed Dr. Velikovsky.

27. That is what he deserved, but it isn't what he got, and that's the point. They didn't roll out a fair person. They rolled out a jealous man who was also a government stooge, which we will get to in a minute. The point I want to make here is that the response of the scientific establishment was cajoled first in 1950 by hatred transposed or transferred from Hubble to him. Questioning the Victorian establishment science (ie, the Royal Society) which lauds itself as the arbiters of truth dating back to Sir Isaac Newton was too much for the Harvard establishment in the early 20th century already. Having this *psychiatrist* out there making successful predictions in the 1950s was just a bridge too far. By the late 1970s, it is clear that their real goal was to terminate his reputation and any movement towards understanding how Nature and science worked.
28. The fact that Hess was chairman of the board is not what interests me. What interests me is how downhill scientific rigor and understanding had gone downhill in the astronomical community between 1963 and 1977. Note that the now discluded "black hole" (classical) and Hawking radiation were invented in this era, and were ignoring evidence of better scientists like I. Langmuir and H. Bostick. Bostick's plasmoid work was published in 1957⁴⁴, but black hole theory came out in 1967⁴⁵. It was the effect of the same mentality killing the Enlightenment since 1927⁴⁶, now in sociology called Critical Theory and in astronomy simply known as Standard Model: an unholy combination of black holes, Big Bang, and dark matter, none of which are compatible with each other or physical reality.

https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafau-na_Extinction

Graham Hancock <gbhancock@gmail.com> Jul 13, 2021, 6:40 AM

Hi Ramon

I just don't see what I can do with or about your material without devoting a great deal of time to it.

That I am not prepared to do as I am deeply immersed in a new project of my own and don't want to divert my energy in the direction of lengthy (if "important") "conversations" with you. I know you are convinced you have found the Holy Grail (so to speak) and perhaps you have. But this is your quest, not mine. I wish you luck and joy on your path.

Best wishes, Graham

Me: Read Between the Lines

If reviewing math and data, evidence, etc. for a renowned researcher is suddenly overwhelming after Velikovsky comes up, what do you think that means? By the way, I love Graham. But in this case he's reached his ceiling. That was Shapley's and Sagan's goals: limit the conversation. It's what Shermer does for a living.

⁴⁴ <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRev.106.404> or <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24941945>

⁴⁵ <https://astronomy.com/magazine/2019/08/a-brief-history-of-black-holes>

⁴⁶ When Big Bang, and not PEMC became the Standard Model, solely on account of Einstein's prestige and a misunderstanding of red shift that wasn't corrected until Halton Arp in the 1980s.

The Paid Government Stooge

Rather than hear me drone on, I'd like to share the info out of Greenwald's book.

Figure 9.1. The cover page of "A Study of Lunar Research Flights," Volume I. Credit: US Army

Figure 1 - Cover page of "A Study of Lunar research Flights," credit: US Army/Greenwald

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Figure 2 - A Study of Lunar research Flights, Project A119; credit: USA/Greenwald

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It isn't necessary for me to know everything the man does. Nor does his involvement in A119 make him a P.O.S. But common sense dictates that the man was chosen as one of a select few for a very secretive project for a reason. Therefore we can tell that he is a **company man**. They don't just let common rabble do it. They vet and they get you signed in. And in particular, you have to promise not to divulge secret or top secret or above top secret to the public, especially without permission and oversight from the boards and intelligence community, etc. Common sense also dictates that anyone circumvents this process for his personal gain, not only is a P.O.S. for putting lives at risk, but a selfish one at that, company man or not.

The Selfish Felon?

I used to have clearance at the [D.O.D.] and I will tell you, point blank, more incensed than I am about the way Sagan treated Velikovsky I am incensed that Sagan potentially, [allegedly] definitely leaked details about Project A119 (its existence only or more?) in order to get a tenured position. That is incredibly selfish. In this case there are no ships to sink. But what about other names and potential spy-agents attached to the project? It seems likely that few, if anyone, was harmed or potentially harmed by this action. But it is both a felony and wrong to do (unethical, and immoral). Therefore I feel fairly certain I can label this an issue of P.O.S. behavior.

*"It ties back to the creation of Dr. Sagan's biography, written by Keay Davidson, entitled, Carl Sagan: A Life. In the course of writing his book, Davidson had outlined some not-so-flattering details about Sagan and his pursuit of trying to make it while he was still very young in his career. The biography detailed the fact that **Sagan may have knowingly revealed classified information in order to increase his chances of winning a Miller Institute graduate fellowship to Berkeley in 1959.** ... So, it was asserted by the author of his biography that Sagan revealed classified information for the judges to take note of his work. Davidson writes:*

[Sagan] decided to confide to [the fellowship judges] information that he was required by federal law to keep secret. He revealed his research at the Armour Research Foundation on the remote detection of lunar nuclear explosions. He must have known the risk he was taking. The information was classified; he had previously cautioned Muller not to discuss it with others... Washington did not look kindly on the leaking of nuclear information."

*I will be clear that the allegation has never been fully substantiated, but when Nature, International Journal of Science published the review of Carl Sagan: A Life, they detailed the story. As a result, Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) requests were filed, and Volume I of "A Study of Lunar Research Flights" was discovered and released to the public. The claims in regard to Sagan's involvement in the plans for detonating a nuclear bomb on the moon were substantiated." ~Greenwald⁴⁷ (and therefore the entire story is given credence, **emphasis** mine)*

It doesn't mean he's evil or deserves to go to Hell. But it's definitely a P.O.S. thing to do.

⁴⁷ Pp. 121

The Fake Apology

One of the most P.O.S. behaviors I despise is obsequiousness: *“obedient or attentive to an excessive or servile degree.”* Think ‘Grima Wormtongue’ and you get my point. The thing that I really despise is a form of it where the doer of wrong begs the audience, his/her willing subjects, to participate in something wrong, then to ‘calm down’ and pretend they are better than that, etc. But in reality, it’s ‘too little too late’ when you ‘let slip the dogs of war’ and then recall them back because they’ve finished ripping the corpse apart (so to speak).

(1) “The worst aspect of the Velikovsky Affair (2) was not that many of his ideas are in gross contradiction to the facts. Rather, the worst aspect is that (3) some scientists attempted to suppress Velikovsky’s ideas. (4) There are many hypotheses in science which are wrong. (5) That’s perfectly alright: it’s the aperture to finding out what’s right,” he further explained, before concluding, (6) “The suppression of uncomfortable ideas (7) may be common in religion or in politics, (8) but it is not the path to knowledge, and (9) there’s no place for it in the endeavor of science.”⁴⁸ ~Dr. C. Sagan

1. The worst aspect of the Velikovsky Affair is clearly that real progress was withheld by means of crushing the *person* and career of Dr. Velikovsky.
2. Which of his ideas are in ‘gross contradiction’? The ones where he was right, or the ones where he questioned the establishment ideas such as gravitation, etc.? One must be curious why the use of the word ‘gross’ (an onomatopoeia if I ever heard one), and it seems to be a form of spite for Velikovsky’s ideas and successes. Psychoanalysis would probably be able to locate a line of envious thinking in this ‘apology’. Certainly it is politician-speak.
3. Some? Can’t name them? Don’t include yourself in this? How ridiculous, considering the public platform and the various means that he publicised his disdain for the ideas and correct conclusions!
4. An understatement which underscores the facts of Science, but obscures the facts that Velikovsky was very often right, and (for them) under ‘unacceptable’ methods. i.e.- using myth to combine with geophysical science to describe human history. Something which, 100 years previously, would have been more than acceptable. It would have been commonplace and just as useful as Darwin’s methods. It is only because of the rise of power of the uniformitarians in geology and the false conclusions of the spectroscopists about the sun being a “ball of burning gas”, and the lack of an atomic and electrical model that anything in his ideas became unacceptable.
5. Completely agree.
6. So Sagan admits that he is uncomfortable with the ideas?
7. Well, if the shoe fits... the suppression of Dr. Velikovsky for questioning (being apostate) the ~~scientific~~ religious (Scientism) establishment perfectly highlights what this is. What Sagan is admitting to here, is the terrible P.O.S. behavior from the establishment, with all its pomp and privilege. Especially Harvard’s Professor Shapley, the man that tried to crush Hubbard and lost, and instead turned his ire to Dr. Velikovsky so he could appeal

to his peers and save face. Organizing book burnings and attacking publishing contracts is absolutely despicable.

8. Right, the path to knowledge is risky. Who took the risk, Sagan or Velikovsky? Who was more right? Who has beat the test of time now that the LHC and CERN have changed the situation with facts? How about the laboratory of space? It has **already been won by the plasma-electromagnetic cosmologists**. But the slain monster is a hydra of many heads that sprout back more, weirder, and more willing to lie (or more likely steal).
9. >>Then why did he help do it?<<

Symptoms of a Wider Issue: Lying Liars Lying

There is an antithesis to the previously cited L^3 power⁴⁹. It's about as Orwellian as $2+2=5$. When Lying Liars are Lying - their mouths are moving or they are writing - they are the worst form of P.O.S. You see, a shoplifter is satisfying a momentary dopamine urge and fulfilling instant gratification. A known issue for those with a low IQ or EQ. However, this is far worse, because it is a) purposeful and premeditated, and b) despicable. What I despise most about it is the brazen willingness to try to force others to accept the lies as real.

This is directly tied to the moochers and the P.O.S. theory in general in this way: liars of this level aren't trying to spare feelings or cover up for sins and transgressions or imperfections. They are embracers of unreality, and more importantly, they violently enforce it. First there is the screeching and lying, then there is the attacks upon reputations, careers, the internet, etc. Next there are riots, burnings, robberies, assaults, and even murders. Finally at the end of the road of all Marxist-Leninism there are gulags, concentration camps, and genocide/etc.

The P.O.S. are liars unrepentant because stealing and mooching are **easy**. They prefer the "easy" road, despite the fact of the paradox of life:

- ★ The hard way is the easy Way.
- ★ The easy way is the hard weigh (burden).

The biggest lie Mrs. Rand identified though, of all the liars in "Atlas Shrugged" was that of her brother, the self-lying liar; a person, a true P.O.S. and spineless coward, of whom she was loyal though eternally ashamed of. He was so cowardly he was willing to take credit for all her work, and let her take the fall if it failed. He did take credit and his wife later found out that he was a charlatan, and threw herself into the sea to drown rather than face her own despondent reality: that he was a wife beating brute P.O.S. who stole the credit of the work of a woman of real steel and courage, and loyalty. The majority of the people in the story are not so overt a P.O.S. as Dagny's brother: they are by and large *standbys*. They are not "passersby" as Yeshua (Jesus) meant it in the Book of Thomas⁵⁰. They are active participants. But, rather than look on and act, they look on and stand by. Some of the worst of this has been exemplified by the iPhone/LiveLeak culture (now worse in TikTok), most demonstrated by the four teens that stood by and laughed as a man literally drowned to death. They filmed it, which was their undoing. Similarly several teens around that time kidnapped a special needs young man and

⁴⁹ https://www.academia.edu/66982437/MIMS_4_21_22_White_and_Black_Spaces_in_Meditation

⁵⁰ Thomas 42, "Be Passersby" (the shortest saying)
<https://www.pbs.org/wgbh/pages/frontline/shows/religion/maps/primary/gthomas.html>

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tortured him, literally, while filming it. I include the screencaps of these in the table below with direct links not to condone the behavior but to expose it. We live in an era where lying liar governments make war in Ukraine, and both sides brazenly lie about what is happening while real people lose homes or are murdered in atrocities. The worst of the Lying Liars - the mainstream media - then covers it up or presents half truths, and the People of the West move on, as if nothing ever happened. This is Orwellianism a la “Animal Farm” style, when the horse is sold for glue, and the pigs use the profits to plot out more butcherings, brazenly. Nothing is done about it, and in the book, the animals never revolt. The west’s cartoon establishment changed this ending to make children feel better. But the only way this really changes is not by wishful thinking, but by really standing up to the moochers, Lying Liars Lying, and the bullies in power. Whatsoever form of the P.O.S. from the religious hypocrite to the corrupt politician and lawyer down to the abusing police officer and his paramour: the perpetual thief-criminal-victim trying to die via “suicide by cop”, et al. They all have to be told “no.”

Table 1 - True Evil Has Been Recorded⁵¹

Figures 3 and 4 - Videographic crimes is a disturbing trend; credit: the criminals' phones

Boundaries - or a lack thereof - are Central to the Issue

In truly abusive relationships, as well as dysfunctional families, what is missing (which religious upbringing is supposed to impart, and did more so in the past), is **boundaries**. These are the P.O.S. that exist because of a lack of boundaries in interpersonal relationships:

1. The Bully
2. The Abuser (and Neglecter)
3. The Perpetual Victim
4. The Codependent
5. The Triangulator
6. The Rescuer → Munchausen by Proxy⁵² is the extreme example

⁵¹ Therefore, the Lying Liars known as “moral relativists” who tell you not to trust your “lying eyes” are nowhere right. They are just as much a part of the P.O.S. issue as the genocidal maniacs and the pacifist enablers. In fact, some of these people are busy trying to convince people that some races should have the right to steal and even kill, and that we should not hold them accountable for crimes or even count the statistics because “statistics are racist.” This kind of evil has to be confronted everywhere, or it will not just spread, it will cause Civil War and Eugenicide (even worse than the abortion fiasco has!)

⁵² <https://medlineplus.gov/ency/article/001555.htm>

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7. The Addict
8. The Enabler
9. The Narcissist
10. The Junkie
11. The Thief
12. The Vampire (toxic polluter and destroyer of Good)
13. The Killer (psychopathic or sociopathic are often here)

None of these people regularly engage in self-building or societal building, and few of them even believe in something larger than themselves for which to be accountable to. They are, often as not, victims of their own internal demons and who knows what external ones?

What they usually lack is a familial background in boundary building and a habit of self-discipline. All of them lack healthy boundaries, and in relationships, too. All of them are Persecutors, but some of them regularly see themselves as the Victim. The problem is that, take for example the Codependent, they only become real victims by first placing others into categories of persecution, inventing stories in their own heads, despite facts or evidence. Then they try to convince others of this internal reality, and instigate situations that should not occur. It is even worse in the Addict or Enabler, which like-as-not lead one another down the path to becoming the Junkie and Rescuer.

Apply this same model of issues to the social situation and one begins to understand the analogs:

1. The Police State
2. The Government
3. The Poor Minority
4. The Corporatocracy
5. The Medical System
6. The Military Industrial Complex (including Deep State)
7. The Welfare Recipient
8. Medicare/Medicaid
9. The Media
10. The Middle Class
11. The IRS
12. Big Pharma
13. Big Tech

The difference between these 13 apostles and the originals should be quite obvious, and yet, each of the original apostles represented the quintessence of the sins of Man. What Yeshua tried to teach each of these men, in the end (and aside from Faith), is the epitome of boundaries. For “fear of the Lord is the beginning of all wisdom.” The very first stories of God’s interactions with Man in Genesis are about boundaries.

- The problems of this world don’t only stem from Sin, but from a deep pervasive misunderstanding of boundary conditions (and rules/norms and their purposes).

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Fundamentally, the issue is that the Internet eliminates boundaries both between people and in morality and ethics. The P.O.S. habituates and abuses this issue by **repeatedly overstepping obvious boundaries**:

- ❖ Good and evil
- ❖ Right and wrong
- ❖ Property and boundary
- ❖ Body and control
- ❖ Image and self-control
- ❖ Logic and lies

When we see this repeated behavior the solutions are, unfortunately, short. First there is warning, then citation, then ultimatum, then war. Finally there is resolution, and if one is lucky: absolutism. However, the far Left and socialists and all their allies are living in a state of trying to nibble away between citation and ultimatum, while pretending war is good. This form of self-loathing arises from a true statement of the ancients:

- ★ Misanlogos... misanthropos - the hatred of words (their real origins and meanings) is tantamount to a hatred of people.

God - the G power - is not against hate. He is against unbridled, undifferentiated, unprincipled hatred. He is most disappointed, though, in apathy in the face of such hate; or a pacifistic avoidance of hate for the sake of the false promotion of unity where Values are not aligned and Truth is obscured by moral relativism. He is also against unfettered and indiscriminate use of anger, therefore:

- *“There are three things all wise men fear: the sea in a storm, a night with no moon, and the anger of a gentle man.” ~P. Rothfuss*

Teaching boundaries is not as easy as learning them, which isn't easy at all. There is a fact of life about boundaries, though: society (and people) cannot function without them.

Cyber-bullies of Scientism, a New Form of P.O.S.!

There is a case of a modern type of Carl Sagan, and he'd more or less love to be compared to Dr. Sagan, to be sure. “Professor Dave,”⁵³ a self-appointed pundit-without-a-purpose who uses the YouTube platform (which is more than happy to use him as a wikipedia like resource, rightfully or wrongfully) to try to bully the Electric Universe, Plasma people (like Ben Davidson and his group, the SuspiciousObservers), and Pierre-Marie Robitaille⁵⁴. Dave abuses his free speech to commit open slander and character defamation. I'll detail it in Table 2 the examples of these P.O.S. videos. However, there is one P.O.S. one of his series which is of particular interest, and that is his Lying Liar Lying treatment of the (regrettably insular and secretive) SAFIRE Project⁵⁵.

⁵³ And “AB Science” who attacked my friend and physics ex-actual-professor, Gareth Samuel.

⁵⁴ Who simply destroyed Dave in a rebuttal. Dave has no clue about spectroscopy and was way out of his league.

⁵⁵ Note even just googling this, to give my audience what the acronym stands for, results in his video coming to the top of google, instead of their own videos! It's **slander**.

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Table 2 - "See the Pattern of Slander and Defamation" - P.O.S. Dave

<p>SuspiciousObservers is a Pseudoscientific Doomsday Cult</p>		
<p>Debunking the Electric Universe</p>	<p>Professor Dave Explains 1.92M subscribers</p> <p>So I put out a debunk video centered on an absurd notion called "The Electric Universe". It pissed off a lot of people, such as a fellow named Ben Davidson, who I had never heard of, but that has a YouTube channel called "SuspiciousObservers" which talks about things sort of tangentially related to this topic. Without any provocation, he took it upon himself to slander me and threaten me by email, before making a ridiculous excuse for a response video countering my debunk. This is my response to his response, because I don't really appreciate being called a fraud, particularly when his response is full of abject nonsense as is his channel in general. Enjoy.</p> <p>UPDATE: Since this video, I've taken it upon myself to dig a lot deeper and I found out precisely what a con man Ben is. Beyond his fraudulent cash grabs on Kickstarter, he is currently busy building a donor-funded apocalypse camp (literally), which makes him a cult leader. More information on his scams can be found in a more recent video which I highly recommend watching and sharing, since there is no telling what horrors will occur on that camp if it gets built: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FTLZ...</p> <p>My original EU debunk video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T9q-v...</p> <p>Solar Physicist Debunks Ben: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_DFyp... Solar Physicist Debunks Ben Part 2: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u8Ocf... Geologist Debunks Ben Some More: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5xS13... A Mountain of Ben Debunking: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uxg9E... Still More: http://whac-a-troll.blogspot.com/2015...</p>	<p>Professor Dave Explains 1.92M subscribers</p> <p>I know that I've become known for my flat earth deceptions, but now that I've driven that one so far into the ground that it's coming out the other side of the spherical earth, it's time to tackle some other topics. There exists an obscure fad called the electric universe, which tends to attract exemplars of the Dunning-Kruger effect who think they understand physics better than Einstein. Literally. Although not quite as ridiculous as the flat earth, it's still pretty ridiculous, so let's go through the finer points of precisely why that is the case, shall we?</p> <p>Watch my other debunks: http://bit.ly/ProfDaveDebunk</p> <p>Classical Physics Tutorials: http://bit.ly/ProfDavePhysics1 Modern Physics Tutorials: http://bit.ly/ProfDavePhysics2 Astronomy Tutorials: http://bit.ly/ProfDaveAstronomy Mathematics Tutorials: http://bit.ly/ProfDaveMath</p> <p>EMAIL ► ProfessorDaveExplains@gmail.com PATREON ► http://patreon.com/ProfessorDaveExplains</p> <p>Check out "Is This Wi-Fi Organic?", my book on disarming pseudoscience! Amazon: https://amzn.to/2HTNpVH Bookshop: https://bit.ly/39cKADM Barnes and Noble: https://bit.ly/3pUjmm Book Depository: http://bit.ly/3aOVDIT</p> <p>SHOW LESS</p>

Figures 5 -10; Dave abusing the truth. Top left to bottom right: Dr. Velikovsky was a genius, this is already covered. SAFIRE is very clearly science, it's just that Dave doesn't know what the scientific method entails, or engineering. His response to Ben Davidson (a lawyer, indeed) was hilarious but wrong, and he should have expected a strong response. If you slander people you can in fact get sued. He isn't wrong, SuspiciousObservers is a Doomsday Cult, but it focuses on real science. The only thing pseudoscientific is the micronova approach, but it's all technically science. As for being a cult, that's self-obvious. The Lie being done here to associate Electric Universe with Flat Earth may or may not be on purpose. As for his assertion that they have Dunning-Kruger, he should probably look in the mirror. Finally, while saying that Ben is grifting might be true, once again it is a P.O.S. thing to do to attack another man's way of living, unless it is criminal. Even if we think it is wrong on some level. It's low character.

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SAFIRE⁵⁶ is in fact [highly proprietary] plasma science, and unique in its temperature achievements and results, but very cautious in what they release. Unlike D. LaPoint⁵⁷, who may be wrong or right but has taken an EPEMC like approach and become open-source⁵⁸ (and will be the subject of a new short paper on Primer Fusion), SAFIRE does not publish papers, for fear of leaking technology and intellectual property out. They appear to want to commercialize their results. Fair enough. But it is **definitely science** (hence funded through International Science Foundation⁵⁹). Nevertheless, it didn't stop self-styled "Professor" Dave from claiming it isn't. Nor was he willing to reconsider his position after I informed him that the mainstream has many textbooks on plasma, and one of electricity in space, titled, "Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond."⁶⁰ Instead he simply told me I couldn't understand it (he doesn't know me from Tuesday⁶¹), and *he dismissed the Wiley/AGU100 publication out of hand*. He is dedicated to Scientism, and do not let the facade of love for Science confuse you otherwise! He is a zealot of the mainstream, and is willing to use his power and abuse his position to hurt others of far more ability, experience, and repute (such as Montgomery Childs et al.). His behaviors are as pure P.O.S. as it gets and he probably deserves a "Peer Review Cult part 2" paper dedicated to him the way I dedicated one to Michael Shermer. But then again, he isn't worth our time. The behaviors of Ben⁶², or the wrongness of Jimmy of "Bright Insight"⁶³ or of the mainstream is worth our time, because it reflects genuine issues. In a new paper forthcoming, "Ashes of Atlantis, Part 2" I will be debunking the esteemed, but wrong, Dr. Zamora, et al. That will be a professional pleasure of mine, I have nothing against him personally nor do I wish him ill. But "Professor" Dave is a P.O.S. and it is clear from the tenor of his videos that he wishes harm to the scientific community with his Scientism, and making a video about SAFIRE is just an example of his ego and hatred, run amok. It is pathetic, but the cyberbullying of the mainstream is worth pointing out when it happens⁶⁴, since there is a burgeoning mainstream science "social media influencer" niche⁶⁵.

Solving the Problem Without Violence as a First Recourse

Mimsically speaking, as war is an anti-MIMS, we need to be proactive about solving the issue of the cycle above. Citation seems too weak, and ultimatums rarely work because of unchecked egos. Using artificial intelligence (AI) to control people is dangerous, but seems

⁵⁶ "SAFIRE is an acronym for "Stellar Atmospheric Function in Regulation Experiment"

<https://www.electricuniverse.info/safire-project/>

⁵⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/d-lapoint>

⁵⁸ <https://primerfieldfoundation.org/technology-transfer>

⁵⁹ <https://www.safireproject.com/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/Electric+Currents+in+Geospace+and+Beyond-p-9781119324492>

⁶¹ And more to the point, how would he know what a stranger knows or doesn't know? A priori fallacy, the mainstream's "Achilles Heel"

⁶²

https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

⁶³ https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1

⁶⁴ Or when they steal altstream ideas and abuse their "in" status to not give credit where credit is due. Eg. Solar Electric Fields.

⁶⁵ Personified by Veritasium, Physics Girl, Backyard Scientist, NighthawkinLight, ElectroBoom, Mark Rober, SmarterEveryDay, etc.

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imminent. The SPACERS™ solution is elegant, but slow (probably too slow). It seems to me, therefore, that the issue really is that there needs to be a step between citation and ultimatum within which the intelligent man, wise woman, and sacred spiritualists are capable of performing the most important part of this: **deescalation**.

But that will not satisfy either of the offended parties. Think about this: the righteous man... can he ever not be offended by the presence of evil and the unrighteous? No. The wicked man or fool, can he ever stop ingratiating himself or learn how not to steal? Not without the Lord (mind-lord or Son of Heaven, etc.). Buddha's form of consciousness-escalation is both too high-minded for the low in WQ⁶⁶, and also insufficient to cause a reformation of the soul that isn't already present (satori⁶⁷ & bodhicitta⁶⁸). Therefore that leaves the work of the A and G powers⁶⁹, through the L^3 power to cause a sufficient alteration in the person with weak boundaries, shamelessness, and a low threshold in virtue (moral or ethical). One cannot forcibly install these programs, and at this time the author has only one non-AI driven solution to offer: technological Charge Distributive Network⁷⁰ flushing. That is to say a *pod* like medical device⁷¹ that emanates the individual with force fields (electromagnetic and plasma-radiological) that use the power of the F and P powers to drive the wickedness (Xie Qi⁷²) out and remove the mind altering protons and reset the DNA and consciousness of the cellular body and psychosomatic body. By resetting this, using the DNA's natural antenna behaviors and particle acceleration, we can evolve humans naturally, without genetic manipulation, fix their relationship to water and food, enhance and fix the issues of the DNA degradation so prevalent because of pollution and poisons everywhere, and hopefully dredge the final vestiges of industrializations' faults. Chiefly: pollution of the outside reflecting pollution of the inside, and then co-creating one another with ever-increasing boundary problems. Koyaanisqatsi⁷³ incarnate can be eradicated and liberalism wouldn't have to die or be controlled. One *could* love thy neighbor the right way: **leave him or her the Hell alone**. Of course it'd be easier to trust and love thy neighbor if they were all energy-fearing people, and not potentially stark-raving-mad and/or pedophiles and other various P.O.S. But I diverge.

Dismantling the Divine Right to Rule False MIMS: elitism doesn't work

The DRR was an evolved fiction that came out of the natural consequence of the god-worship from the time before the death of the Shamash/Is/Ra/El star, through the end and all the way through tribalism until the medieval era. Man slowly - ever so slowly - began to

⁶⁶ The best definition for Wisdom Quotient I have seen is IQ+EQ. So for example my IQ is 133.7 and EQ is 100, therefore my WQ (data side at least) is 233.7/400 (with sigma=20 that is 96.3%, sigma=10, 99.9%)

⁶⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Satori>

⁶⁸ <https://tricycle.org/magazine/what-is-bodhicitta/>

⁶⁹

http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

⁷⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

⁷¹ This device is within my capacities to create, but funding is the main issue, and of course time and other limitations.

⁷² “邪 · xié · evil influence” <https://chinese.yabla.com/chinese-english-pinyin-dictionary.php?define=xie+qi>

⁷³ “Life out of Balance”; see the film by the same name.

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realize that the Philosopher-King⁷⁴ is a nearly useless fantasy. After all, the reality is that for every 'positive' Caesar, there are 20 generations of incestuous fools and crazies⁷⁵. How the traditions of the shaman and chiefs became that of the astrologer/mage-wizards and kings is probably a long story and full of guesses. But it isn't hard to see that if you kill the elders and chief, kidnap the children and women, incorporate their stories into yours which are similar, you can consolidate power and provide a means for controlling both (or more) parties by saying "my gods made me king." In the age of Ordered Religion that became bureaucratic power, and from there a legitimate threat of force formed against the supposed apostates and infidels. But in reality it's just control of the populace, naturally. That's always the first priority of the state. And from there, the anti-MIMS known as war becomes the second highest priority⁷⁶.

So why do the elites of this world want a return? Let's be clear, it is not only an oligarchic form of capitalism⁷⁷ where this is present, but also Anglo-American (board dominated) capitalism. It's probably because mankind is full of egotistical needs, such as fears of death and the unknown, a need to control the uncontrollable threats, and the desire for fame, fortune, and immortality. These things are easy to see and understand. What isn't so easy for the populace to see, either the elite or the rabble, is why it doesn't work and why it should be obvious it can never work. Think about this, how could a finite mortal control \$10 trillion in equity⁷⁸ by his near lonesome, and *not* cause a catastrophe? Eventually there'd be a failure. It is inevitable⁷⁹. And so we see the Blackrock people now admit - only after the end of all the power of fiat as Chussia

(China-Russia Capital-Communist bloc) moves back to gold. The Derivatives meltdown just might be imminent. No one knows for sure, but looking at the money velocity it seems to be certain to me.

Figure 11 - US decline shown in money velocity; credit: USC Economics Review

Conclusion

In the end the way we eradicate the P.O.S. is not to sit back and wait til they violate all boundaries when **everybody knows it**. Socially, that might be too late. For humanity, it's almost

⁷⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/philosopher-king>

⁷⁵ https://www.eupedia.com/history/best_and_worst_roman_emperors.shtml

⁷⁶ "1 Sun Tzu said: The art of war is of vital importance to the State.

2 It is a matter of life and death, a road either to safety or to ruin. Hence it is a subject of inquiry which can on no account be neglected." ~Sunzi Bingfa ("The Art of War")

⁷⁷ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4224929>

⁷⁸ <https://www.ft.com/content/7dfd1e3d-e256-4656-a96d-1204538d75cd>

⁷⁹ See the Epilogue of the "Peer Review Cult" paper, Ibid.

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certainly going to be too late. Therefore the author recommends we primarily use technology - but in a mode of respect to the Laws⁸⁰ beneath the *P* power, primarily a polar complete physics - to eradicate field *misaligned* issues. A device that could press the charges out might reduce the charges in courts. But would it solve the issue of the soul's polar nature? The lack of P.O.S. controls have clearly exceeded acceptable levels. When Duke Energy and others can pollute and pay nominal fees⁸¹, and the government can put ankle bracelets on innocent people for being 'guilty' of a positive diagnosis (using faulty kits) of COVID⁸², then it is clear the issue is out of control. Putting non-criminals in prison, or concentration camps⁸³, and turning obvious self-defense cases into "federal cases."⁸⁴ Then the media castigates the patriot, or innocent, and props up the obvious P.O.S. (like George Floyd⁸⁵), and gaslights the public about it.

What is obvious from looking at the story of Dr. Sagan is that truly "*the only thing for evil to triumph over good is for good men to do nothing.*" This is a man of access, and of ability, and he was too narcissistic to hold himself to a certain code of behavior. But worse than that is that no one stopped him, or was willing to get in front of his freight train of bullshit and **sophistry**.

Figure 12 - Hancock Wrecks a Train (assuredly killing the conductor and engineer) ([gif](#)); credit: "Hancock"/Columbia Pictures⁸⁶

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

⁸⁰ Causality, Evolution/Flux, Relativity, Conservation, Vibration, Rotation, Polarity, & Resonance

⁸¹

<https://publicintegrity.org/environment/duke-energy-fined-25-1-million-for-groundwater-damage-from-coal-ash/>

⁸²

www.wkyt.com/2020/07/18/hardin-co-couple-gets-ankle-monitors-after-covid-19-quarrel-with-health-dept/

⁸³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mGFdWcJU7-0>

⁸⁴ Eg. Kyle Rittenhouse

⁸⁵ Who died of fentanyl induced "Excited Delirium" for which a manslaughter charge became murder

⁸⁶ The irony of the gif being shared on the right is that this person played an individual with incredible power, but serious character flaws, and he showed off this at the recent Academy Awards. His wife is a P.O.S. and he is so twisted inside that he also has become a P.O.S. and the victim was behaving like a P.O.S., too. All of this is an issue of a social convention (Hollywood) that is lacking boundaries.